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Vision-based control for track geometry optimization of complex AM motion profiles by on-line laser power modulation

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Abstract

In the metal additive manufacturing technique known as Direct Metal Deposition, parts are manufactured by blowing metal powder particles into a laser beam moved according to a predefined path. The trajectories the laser source follows usually include several changes of direction, in which local increase of energy density occurs due to both high curvature and deceleration/acceleration ramps the machine axis motion has to perform. This increase results in the typical presence of local over-deposition.

Deposition tracks with uniform profiles are relevant especially when parts are composed by a significant number of layers and/or when short zig-zag tracks are preferred to longer linear tracks to avoid risks for thermal and mechanical distortion in large parts. The real-time measurement of an appropriate indicator for anomalous growth phenomena allow to dynamically correct for higher weld seam and finally part quality.

This work presents a closed-loop control system able to adjust on-line the power of the laser beam according to the feedback provided by the analysis of meltpool images. The images are acquired by means of a camera mounted coaxially into the optical chain of the deposition head, which records images at 100 fps while the deposition is running. The benefits of the proposed approach are demonstrated experimentally by comparing the resulting over-deposition on sample test geometries with respect to the over-deposition obtained on a reference commercial open-loop laser deposition system.

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1. Introduction

Direct Metal Deposition (DMD) is an additive manufacturing technology where a stream of metal particles carried by a gas - blown from a set of nozzles - are fused with the energy delivered by a laser beam, forming a *melt pool*. The beam both melts these particles and remelts the underlying portion of substrate. While the deposition process advances, the melt pool evolves into a solid metal *track* (Fig. 1).

A multitude of physical phenomena, ranging from fluid dynamics of the stream and heat dissipation to material growth and microstructure, contributes to the process [1-2]. The combination of these phenomena and laser spot motion dynamics induces heterogeneity of the track shape, thus

Fig. 1. Direct Energy Deposition process.

Fig. 2. Dimensional irregularities caused by machine feed ramps at the workpiece corners.

representing the major cause of dimensional problems in DMD parts (both in the contour and infill of each single layer – Fig. 2) and leading to poorly robust industrial components [3], e.g. parts with large geometric distortions or with internal defects that compromise the mechanical performances. To increase the quality of such a promising manufacturing technique, the research community has been facing the challenge of simulating DMD with multi-physics based approaches, ranging from analytical process modelling [4] to the use of FEM tools for the description of the deposition growth and the related thermal and mechanical distortion effects [5].

Such modelling approaches are impractical for depositing real parts by DMD, even off-line, during process planning, due to the computational burden and the high number of unknown parameters involved in the process.

For this reason, process recipes for DMD are usually designed by relying on less refined statistical models based on preliminary characterization tests, which would be necessary even in presence of a robust physics-based simulation model. The relation between process parameters and deposition outcomes is modelled by regression analysis, integrating data gathered both on-line, during the deposition process, and off-line, after the prototype part is built [6].

However, these open-loop models are not sufficient to achieve the quality KPIs (geometric accuracy, density, yield stress) required in various applications. Local, unpredictable process variations or very complex thermal and mass transfer phenomena occur even in commonly used deposition strategies, leading to undesired material deposition performance. This makes on-line process control essential to overcome above mentioned restrictions, and to improve thereby the performance of DMD machines [7-8-9].

Existing on-line control models for metal AM have been developed mainly for the Powder Bed Fusion technology, and they are not straightforwardly adaptable to DMD [10], while the few existing approaches to vision-based on-line control in DMD have been tailored for the control of specific geometric features [11]

This paper presents a closed-loop control strategy that adapts laser power by using information acquired by melt pool camera

Fig. 3. Proposed closed-loop control strategy.

images, as shown in Fig. 3, with the aim to reduce local over-deposition defects. The presented control strategy can enhance the performance of DMD machines in printing dimensionally sound components.

2. Process model

DMD process models associate the main deposition outcomes (track size and shape and structural properties) to a multitude of effects:

- the fluid-dynamics of blown powders, and in particular the percentage of powder particles that fall into the melt pool;
- specific energy, i.e. the ratio between laser power P and laser spot diameter $2r$ times traverse speed V :

$$E = \frac{P}{2rV};$$

- the geometry and surface quality of the underlying substrate or previously deposited material;
- the tool path strategy, i.e. the laser spot trajectory.

Only a subset of the aforementioned parameters is controllable in an open-loop system. For example, specific energy is known to have a monotone increasing relation with deposition rate [12] (at least in a reasonable range of operating values). On the other side, although it is known that substrate temperature and geometry have a heavy influence on deposition results, it is often not possible to know them in real-time or to characterize completely the process behaviour considering its infinite possible operating conditions. A feedback-based approach would reveal the potential to dynamically adjust process fluctuations to achieve specific KPIs, without needing to refer to a specific, previously tested geometry/material/strategy and deposition history.

This work presents a process monitoring approach that:

1. **exploits on-line vision data:** since beam-coaxial process monitoring cameras are present in most available DMD machines, the controller exploits a simple and cost-effective monitoring solution.
2. **aims at controlling track geometries:** local variations of energy density and heat drift influence track size; these phenomena may be revealed by the processing of melt pool images, thus allowing for geometry control by power-based closed-loop control.

The proposed monitoring and control solution has been implemented in the simple and yet robust framework of proportional-integral process control: the considered monitoring signal is compared to a desired value, which can be considered a proxy of track height, and the residual is used to generate a new control action for laser power.

3. Process control methodology

3.1. Reference experiment: the V-tracks

The baseline geometric features taken into account in this work are single tracks with corners (*V-tracks* in the following, see Fig. 4), as a test bench for the vision-based process control solution.

Such features represent one of the main building blocks of

Fig. 4. V-track with 20° corner and 10 mm segment length.

almost any complex deposition, i.e. performing trajectories with changes of direction or curvature (see Fig. 5 for some typical examples of infill trajectories for the deposition of a part single layer).

The interesting phenomenon that can be observed in V-tracks is the typical presence of *over-deposition*, i.e. anomalous height and/or width of the track section, in the corner location (Fig. 6), where both the high curvature and the acceleration ramps of the machine axis motion induce a local increment of energy density and a higher incident powder flow per surface unit [14]. It additionally demands a trajectory that embeds in the linear portions of the feature two acceleration and deceleration ramps and very limited constant speed profiles: the three aforementioned motion profiles typically have an impact on the resulting deposited track. The need for regular profile deposition corners can be appreciated even more with large parts, where depositing long tracks would pose major risks for thermal-mechanical distortion and therefore very angled and shorter tracks are preferred.

Being able to measure in real-time an indicator of anomalous growth phenomena can thus be very useful to correct it dynamically, without the need to base process control on a previously collected anthology of deposition results observed after different deposition plans, as demonstrated in [15].

3.2. Monitoring method

The developed equipment setup consists of a 3-axis laser machine with an Optomec multi-nozzle deposition head. The head includes a slot for connecting a c-mount camera for a beam-coaxial view of the melt pool, thanks to a dichroic mirror that reflects the emitted radiation, filtering out the high-power laser frequencies, i.e. a narrow band around 1080 nm (Fig. 7). The camera is a FLIR Grasshopper 3, equipped with a 2.3 Mpix CMOS SonyIMX174 colour sensor and connected via GigaEthernet to a dedicated PC that receives and stores the images acquired at 100 fps during the deposition process.

The post deposition quality inspection (track geometry) is executed by means of a Keyence VHX-6000 digital microscope with zoom lenses up to 2000X for a spatial resolution of 0.11 μm/pixel.

After testing various image processing methods, the mean image intensity I (in the following simply “intensity”) of

Fig. 5. Typical single layer infill trajectories, from [13].

Fig. 6. V-track height profile: highest value in correspondence of the corner.

images converted to greyscale was found to be a good indicator of the occurring over-deposition due to the local increase in energy density at the V-track corner. In fact, average image intensity increases both due to higher melt pool temperature and to larger melt pool size, which occur during the passage through the V-track corner. Moreover, its computation is very fast, so that it does not represent a bottleneck for the control loop execution time.

Fig. 8 shows the intensity values retrieved by images captured during two different deposition tests. The intensity presents a peak at the beginning of the return branch of the V-track, i.e. when the speed is minimum and the laser beam tends to spend more time on the same track portion.

The correlation between image intensity and profile height is confirmed by the microscope measurements as reported in Fig. 8: the track presents a bulk in correspondence of the track inversion corner.

3.3. Process control model

The objective of the control strategy is to enable the deposition of a track that has a uniform height, matching the desired one. A preliminary experimental campaign run on single tracks has determined the relations:

$$h = f(P, V), \quad I = g(P, V, \mathbf{M}),$$

where h represents track height and \mathbf{M} represents monitoring settings (e.g. exposure time, gain and white balancing). When the optimal \mathbf{M} is established as a function of P and V , we can

Fig. 7. Deposition head and optical paths (left); example of top view melt pool images acquired by the camera (right).

Fig. 8. Intensity values along the deposition: peak in correspondence of the V-track corner. H represents peak height with respect to the signal average in linear section, while W represents peak width.

obtain indirectly a relation $I = I(h)$ between image intensity and deposition height, which are in fact correlated.

The correlation between track height and image intensity allows adopting the following approach:

1. Use the process map $h = f(P)$ to decide the nominal power P_{nom} to be used during the whole deposition to obtain the desired track height \bar{h} . This yields also $\bar{I} = I(\bar{h})$.
2. Stabilize I in time around the target value \bar{I} . Since I is a proxy of h , its regularity allows to achieve a uniform track height.

The stabilisation of image intensity is realized through the implementation of a PI (proportional-integral) controller (Fig. 9). A derivative component has not been included as, after intensive testing, it yielded no significant benefits to the reduction of signal settling oscillations.

The tuning of the PI control is performed first of all by commanding a random input (power) signal to the dynamic system (the DMD machine) and acquiring the sensor feedback, i.e. the mean image intensity. The unknown dynamic system is then identified as a state-space model, using the subspace method. The estimation yielded a stable fourth degree state-space model, coherently with the similar model identification approach used in [16]. Fig. 10 shows the comparison between a validation signal, generated with a new input, and its simulation by the identified model, which provides a good prediction of the model output.

The identified model has been then used to evaluate the step response and consequently to tune the K_p and K_I parameters. The results of the tuning are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: PI tuning results.

K_p	2.5
K_I	0.1
Rise time	80 ms
Sample time	10 ms

4. Approach validation and experimental results

The reference material for the experimental campaign is high carbon content steel K890 powder, with grain size range 40–100 μm ; K890 presents good hardness, but its low weldability makes it a challenging material to employ in AM. The base plates present the same chemical composition of the deposited

Fig. 9. PI controller diagram.

material and a thickness of 12 mm.

The nominal power levels P_{nom} required to obtain different heights at fixed velocity $V = 100$ mm/min have been determined by a preliminary campaign on single tracks, performed on a grid from 100 to 1000 W with step 100 W. The obtained look-up table has been further optimized to determine a comprehensive set of process recipes ensuring the desired reference heights. The preliminary deposition runs have been exploited to capture the image intensities while keeping V and the vision settings \mathbf{M} fixed (in particular exposure time 10 ms). This generates the required function g for image intensities in relation to P, V, \mathbf{M} .

V-tracks have been deposited multiple times, using as process parameters $P = 300$ W, $V = 100$ mm/min and a powder flow rate of 30 mg/s. Five reference V-tracks have been deposited without melt pool control, while five samples with the same process parameters have been deposited with the melt pool control loop enabled, using the parameter values described in Section 3.3.

For each track the peak height was measured in the corner region, while track height in linear regions (before and after the corner) has been determined by averaging the measurements taken in 80 different points along the track centreline (40 on the first branch and 40 on the second branch of the V shape). The resulting track heights in linear regions presented mean values in the range 562–779 μm and standard deviations in the range 42–63 μm . Compared to peak heights in the corners (931–1142 μm) the track heights resulted significantly different, as confirmed by one-sided Wilcoxon tests (p-values < 1e-3 in all cases).

The over-deposition ratios, i.e. the ratios between peak height and linear section height of each track, have been averaged across the repetitions with and without power control enabled. The results, resumed in Table 2, show that in tracks deposited with melt pool control enabled the over-deposition in the corner region (see Fig. 11) is reduced (~17% of the track

Fig. 10. Validation of estimated dynamic system: measured intensity signal (dashed line) and simulated output (green line).

height in linear regions). A Wilcoxon test confirms this difference, yielding a p-value lower than 5% for a one-sided two-samples test.

Table 2: Deposition tests summary

	Open loop		Closed loop	
	mean	st. dev.	mean	st. dev.
Over-deposition ratio (averaged on 5 tracks)	1.66	0.08	1.49	0.07

5. Conclusion and future works

The article shows improved dimensional accuracy of metal V-tracks printed by DMD. The proposed closed-loop control system running on a 3 axes machine optimises the laser power in relation to the melt pool image intensity captured with an in-axis camera sensor. As a result of an efficient PI process control model, the profile of the deposited track reduces height overshootings of 17% and such improvement is to be appreciated especially in the V-tracks corners where the risk of over-deposition is quite high as a result of the machine tool deceleration and acceleration motion profiles.

The proposed control model will be scaled to new alloys starting with other high carbon content steel alloys that typically embrace most of the challenges in regular material growth by AM. Next steps will also pertain to the realization of single layers and 3D bulks where the deposition strategy demands several motion inversions. Finally, comprehensive activities are under development with regard to the implementation of more complex control approaches, such as GPC based on the identified dynamical model of the process, and the integration of additional feedback and look-ahead signals, like the instantaneous laser spot velocity.

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Fig. 11. Reduction in over-deposition at the corner of a V-track executed with active power control.

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